

Royal Services of Transgender in India during the Medieval Period: Special Reference to Eunuchs

Mr. J. Pushparaj Ph.D.,
Research scholar,
Department of History, Annamalai University,
Annamalai Nagar- 608 002, Tamil Nadu

A B S T R A C T

This article has focused on revealing the significance of Eunuchs and their royal service in royal household, especially Islamic Kings like Sultans and Mughals. The transgender were renewed as Eunuchs in Medieval period. The transgender were marginalized in the social, economical and political platform in contemporary era. But they were received highest position during the medieval period. Eunuchs served as the confidants, Cooks, waiters, Messengers, Bed keepers, Chamberlains, Kitchen guards, commander of the army, Singers , writers, Mansabdars, Generals , de factor ruler, charge of treasury, master of wardrobe, and political advisors in the Royal harem. They were received titles likes other nobles, and also mansabdars. Indeed, their service might be the prominent services other than slaves and women. However, their royal service had been forgotten in the history of India, even unsung in the history of India.

Keywords: Eunuchs, Royal service, Mughal Harem, Islamic Kings, Sultans and Mughals.

Introduction

Indian History was written by scholars to glorify the successes and failures of the Kings and queens, which were based on the male or female gender. But the other gender, or third gender, was partially or completely neglected in history. In the meantime, the third gender has played a crucial role in history through the ages. In the Archaic period, third genders were glorified as Lords, and they were mentioned in the epics in the mythological version. During the medieval period, the third gender received the highest dignity, especially on the Mughal *harem*¹. The third genders were renowned as ‘*Eunuchs*’ in the Islamic world, as also noted in the Sultanate and Mughal regimes, even contemporary period. This term ‘*Eunuchs*’ was used for census of 1981 A.D.,² The employment of eunuchs in the imperial *harem* was necessary to maintain the dignity of the queens. They were served from the lowest job to the highest position, which depicted that they played a crucial role in the king’s palace. Eunuchs served as the confidants, Cooks, waiters, ³Messengers, Bed keepers, ⁴Chamberlains,⁵ Kitchen guards, ⁶commander of the army⁷, Singers⁸, writers, *Mansabdars*, ⁹Generals, de factor ruler, ¹⁰charge of treasury, master of wardrobe, and political advisors in the Royal harem. Under the leadership of Islamic kings in India, they recruited the transgender high volume, also they named as *Eunuchs*. However, their service is not recognized or neglected in the historical accounts. This article has focused on revealing the significance of *Eunuchs* and their royal service in royal household, especially Islamic Kings like Sultans and Mughals.

Nomenclature

Transgender are renowned wide range of identities like Akwa, *Aravani* Aravanis, Aradhis Aqua, Chhinni, Chhibri, *Chakka kinnar* Eunuchs, *Jogtas/Jogappas*, *Hijiras*, Kinner, Khadra, Khoja, *Kothis*, Khusra¹¹, Khawajasira,¹² Kinnars, Kojja, kothis, Mangalamukhi, Napunsaka, Pavaiyaa, Sakhi-Bekhi, Shiva-Shakthis, *Shiv-shak*, Shandha, Nupi-Maanba Thirunangis and Cross dressers (*zenena*). The Islamic kings has been used the term eunuchs during the medieval period. The word eunuch is belongs to the Greek word *Euneukhos* (*euvouxoc*) which literally means attendants of the bed chamber in royal households. Some scholars believe the term derives from the amalgam of the Greek terms for “bed” and “keep” in courts.¹³ The dictionary

gives the etymology of the word as being derived from the Middle English 'eunuk' from Latin 'eunuchus', from the Greek 'eunouchos'. From 'eunc' i.e., bed plus 'echein' which means 'to have or have charge of' the Oxford English dictionary defines the word as a man who has been castrated, especially (in the past) one employed to guard the women's living areas at an oriental court and an intellectual person, thus we may have a nation of political eunuchs.

Harem

Harem was the imperial household in Sultanate and Mughal period, where Kings wives, concubines, family members, servants, slaves resided. The word Harem itself is derived from the Arabic harem, meaning protected or forbidden. It refers to the physical and spiritual isolation of women confined in a specific place. Harem quarters were a domestic world with the celebration of births, marriages and deaths, religious festivals, and social occasions.¹⁴ The harem eunuch presents a particularly ancient use of castrated males, which were partly for profit, as well as prestige and pleasure.

Castration

Eunuchs were the castrated males who have desire to work on Mughal harem. A castrated person employed to take charge of women of a harem and act as chamberlain are known as eunuch. The process of castration originated from the tradition of desexualizing the animals, a string or horse hair is tied around the scrotum, which results testicles turn black and drop off in about three weeks, apparently discomfort to the animal. Another way the testicles were crushed off through hands or rocks, or cutting them off a knife.¹⁵ Manucci registered about the slave trade of eunuchs in his travelogues; Eunuchs who have worked in the Mughal harem were both kidnapped or sold from the Indian parents. Some of them were brought from the other countries Egypt, Sudan and Ethiopia, and Middle Eastern areas.¹⁶

Royal titles

Eunuchs are worked in the royal household honored by the kings through the royal titles. The most appropriate term for the community, Khwaja sira as it was commonly used. Historically, the head eunuch had been called as Khwaja sira. Manucci gives a list of about 40

Nazirs of the time of the Aurangzeb, each of them whom had a separate tile bestowed upon him by the King, like nadir, Nadiyah, Danish, Daulat, Yusuf, Yaqut, Almas, Maqbul, Neknam, Amanant and Atibar.¹⁷

Royal Kitchen

The royal kitchen, like everything else associated with royalty, was a large and tightly organized establishment. Fernao Nuniz, a Portuguese traveler resided that “The king has ten important cooks for his personal service, where other not allowed preparing or serving the food.” The Kitchen has secured by the guards, mostly by the Eunuchs, where people were restricted for the fear of poison. When the king wishes to eat every person withdraws, and then some of the women whose duty it is, and they prepare the table for him. Manucci registered that the eunuchs were took charge of preventing all illicit foods, drugs and beverages entered in the royal harem.¹⁸

In charge of Royal household

Eunuchs were basically made the in charge of the entire royal household as the women residence. The chief eunuch was it attended by female servants. Naturally two or three eunuchs or even highest numbers recruited for the faithful servants to each wife of the King. These eunuchs were enjoyed a lot of freedom and privileges. They were attire in rich clothes of fines embroidery with gold and silver thread on silk and muslin. Eunuchs were received highest position, they could desire like great horses and servants. They were provided with fine clothes with highest quality as fine as smart as those of their master himself. Around thirty to forty footmen attended on the *umara* to make way for them, and walked along those carrying lances, fans, umbrella and palkis and other attendants to carry Pots full of water and Tobacco pipes.¹⁸ Most of the eunuchs stationed outside the harem, were appointed on guard duty. The senior eunuchs were called as Nazirs or Khawaja siras. Everyone had a group of eunuchs under him. There cadre was hierarchical. According to Manucci, “There is always one set above the rest who directs and looks after everything that goes on in the Mahal”. The chief Nazir have more privilege and possessed the title of Aitbar Khan which means ‘the trusted Lord’.

Governors and Commanders

The eunuchs are worked not only the basic duties, also taking in charge of the region, as Governors. The one Aitbar Khan was served under the King of Babur and Humayun. During Akbar period, one Aitbar Khan chaperoned Akbar's Mother and other Ladies of Royal household from Kabul to Hindustan safely. As a reward for his duty, the King appointed him as the Governor of Delhi. Another eunuch has received the title of Aitamad Khan rendered great service to the Mughals. His real name was Phool Malik and he was worked under Salim Shan Sur. He was honored with the title of Muhammad Khan. While Akbar came to the throne, Muhammed Khan entered the royal service to the Mughal emperor and help to improving financial service which already damaged of Maham Anaga. He made him as a commander with 1000 battalions and conferred the title of Aitmad Khan.

In 1565, Aitmad Khan safeguarded the daughter of Miran Mubarak Shah, King of Khandesh to Akbar's harem. Then he took part in the conquest of Bengal, also he was appointed governor of Bhakkar. He finds a place in the list of Akbar's grantees. Aitmad Khan erected Itmadpur, distance of six kos from Agra. He possessed there a village and a large tank. After his death he was buried there.

Another Aitmad Khan was worked under Sultan Mahmud of Gurajat, received good name. Then he got the appointment in the Akbar's service. He travelled to Mecca for paid his devotion, while he brought a big stone have the impression of the foot of the prophet. He was appointed governor of Gujarat and was a commander of 4000 soldiers. During Jahangir period, the chief eunuchs titled Aitbar Khan appointed as Governor of Agra city. He also enjoyed privileges like other governors, had own palaces near river Jumna in Agra. He was the favorite person of Jahangir.¹⁹

Mansabdaras

Many Khwaja Saras and Nazirs thus were men of importance. Some of them rose to the position of Mansabdar. A Eunuch namely Firoz Khan was conferred a mansab of around 1500 by Jahangir. Bakhtawar Khan, superintendent of the eunuchs under Aurangzeb held the rank of

thousand. He also turned out to be a scholar and a historian and wrote the Mirat-ul-Alam and the Mirat-i-Jahan Numa. He also prepared an abridgement of the Tarkh-i-Alfi and Akhbar-ul-Akhiyar. Eunuchs were given great loyalty and received important position like Mansabdars.²⁰

In-charge of Treasury

The term eunuch also has the meaning of Treasurer. Eunuchs were also worked as the in charge of treasury in the royal household. According to Manucci, the chief Nazir of the seraglio, “is highly esteemed by the king, He has a large allowance, has charge of treasury, is master of wardrobe, decides on the details and the pattern of Sarapas to be prepared in short, it is he who has in charge of all the Mughal expenditure of the clothes, the linen, and the precious stones, of the jewelry, of everything that goes into or comes out of the place. Such a powerful person could easily mass wealth done by Nazir-ud-daula, an important eunuch of Akbar. These proved that the Eunuchs were the important person in the Mughal royal service.”²¹

De facto Rulers

Eunuchs are paid their loyalty and nearness to the King and queens. Their wise knowledge and visionary ideas, lead the great influence in government and politics. There were three eunuchs ruled the state behalf of Mughalgani Begam namely Mian Khushfahan, Mian Mahabat and Arimand.²²

Malik Kafur

Throughout both the Hindu and Muslim periods of Indian rulers, eunuchs were employed in the harems and palaces of the queens Malik Kafur was an originally a Hindu eunuch of Gujarat. He was very handsome and intelligent. IN 1297 he was purchased for 1000 Dinars by Nusrat Khan. This is the reason Malik Kafur is sometimes called Hazar-Dinari. Ala-ud-din was hugely impressed by the wise knowledge of Malik Kafur, later he received the highest rank of Naib Kafur within ten years. Also he got the title of Malik Taj-ul-Malik Kafuri. Malik kafur was responsible for the conquest of the South. Ala-ud-din put Malik Kafur in charge of Deccan campaign and the latter brought him victories, wealth and reputations. Malik Kafur enjoyed the affection of the sultan from the start. He rose to become a general in the Sultan’s army and

raided and looted temple and palaces of South Kingdoms of the Yadavas, Kakatiyas and Pandayas many times. After he captured Devagiri, he was appointed the Governor of Devagiri. However, when Allaudin fell sick, Malik Kafur was recalled to be by his side. He was the most trusted aide of the sultan and exercised the de facto powers of the Sultan during his last days. Many scholars allude to a romantic relationship between Malik Kafur and Allaudin.²³

Messengers

Some of the eunuchs or subordinate eunuchs were worked as messengers in the harem. They carried sealed letters to addressees and brought back replies. Some of them worked as doorkeepers, monitored whoever went in or out of the Mahal. Entry inside the Mahal was meticulously checked by them. Whenever a person was let in, his name, physiognomy and other details were carefully noted down on a pattern and verified at many check points. Physicians who went inside the harem to treat patients were similarly scrutinized. Bernier went to the seraglio on the occasion. He was permitted to the Harem with covering his head by a Kashmir Shawl, also a large scarf covered up to his feet. While eunuchs were leading his hand to bring him inside the harem. Thus the eunuchs monitored everyone and authorized the person who entered the seraglio. Roshanara Begum, Aurangzeb's sister, used her trusted *kwajasaras* to circulate confidential information regarding her brother's illness. Another *kwajasaras* was made the guardian of Aurangzeb's son in case Aurangzeb did not recover from his illness.²⁴

To sum up, transgenders were faced several obstacles in the social, economical and political platform. But they were received the highest position during the medieval period. Eunuchs played a crucial role in the royal household, from doorkeeper to de facto rulers. Eunuchs were only people to communicate the Kings and queens, even protectors of royal ladies. They were received titles like other nobles, and also *mansabdars*. Indeed, their service might be the prominent services other than slaves and women. However, their royal service had been forgotten in the history of India, even unsung by the scholars. Thus, the eunuchs played a crucial role in the Mughal harem during the medieval period.

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